

Evaluating Coaching Effectiveness to Improve Performance at Rumah Zakat

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ABSTRACT: Rumah Zakat is a philanthropic institution that manages, collects, and empowers zakat, infaq, and sadaqah funds. It was established in 1998 under the name Ummul Quro Social Wallet (DSUQ). Currently, to enhance employee performance and optimize organizational results, Rumah Zakat emphasizes the involvement of leaders in the team development process. In previous years, Rumah Zakat managers underwent training related to leadership skills to optimize their roles. In this context, one crucial aspect of a manager's role is to engage in the coaching process. Effective coaching by a manager can significantly impact individual behavior change and improve organizational results. However, in reality, not all managers can properly optimize the coaching process and their role as coaches in the workplace. Several issues have arisen among participants in the employee improvement program regarding the involvement of leaders or managers in team development.

Therefore, based on the situation, there is a need for a comprehensive evaluation of the coaching process conducted by all managers at Rumah Zakat to immediately implement improvements and provide training to optimize coaching effectiveness. In this study, using quantitative methodology, primary data was gathered from Rumah Zakat employees who completed a set of questionnaires. This survey will be distributed specifically to employees at the officer level who often interact directly with their leaders at Rumah Zakat. To determine the number of samples, this paper uses Slovin's formula with a confidence level of 95%, resulting in 213 samples with a margin of error of 5%. Furthermore, the results will be followed up with a qualitative phase using semi-structured interviews. From these results, it is indicated that the implementation of coaching effectiveness tends to be at a medium level for all components. This suggests that the coaching process has been implemented and is reasonably optimal, but the assessment is still at a medium stage, indicating the need for improvements.

KEYWORDS: Coaching Evaluation, Effectiveness, Philanthropic Institution, RACSR framework.

I. INTRODUCTION

This chapter introduces the background, company profile, and business issues that will be discussed throughout the research. This research presents research questions, objectives, scope, and limitations as the fundamental part of the research

A. Background

A rapidly changing world requires companies to be able to adapt and be ready to accept challenges in order to improve performance optimally. For this reason, in order for a company to be competitive and ready to face the existing changes, it is necessary to prepare qualified human resources. All companies operating in various industries, including philanthropic organizations, need to prepare quality and effective human resources to compete and be ready to face various challenges. A company will be able to demonstrate good performance if there is a synergistic relationship among various stakeholders within it. In this regard, the relationship between managers and employees and the involvement of leaders in the team development process play crucial roles. One important role of a manager is to engage in the coaching process. According to Kampa-Kokesch and Anderson (2001), coaching is a form of systematic feedback intervention designed to enhance an employee's professional skills, interpersonal awareness, and personal effectiveness. Previous research on managerial roles has stated that coaching is perceived as a tool to address employee performance deficiencies (Mace & Mahler, 1958). This process involves communicating with an employee for the purpose of improving on-the-job performance or behavior (Hall, Otazo, and Hollenbeck, 1999).

Rumah Zakat is a philanthropic institution that manages, collects, and empowers zakat, infaq, and sadaqah funds. Currently, to enhance the performance of employees and optimize organizational results, Rumah Zakat drives the leader's role to be involved in the team development process. Effective coaching by a manager can significantly impact individual behavior change and improve organizational results. Based on the Center for Creative Leadership coaching model, to be able to implement coaching effectiveness

properly, there are 5 critical components that are interconnected, namely RASCR, *Relationship, Assessment, Challenge, Support*, and *Result*, and in it, there are 9 competency components that must be possessed by leaders and needed in the development process team. This research will focus on evaluating the coaching process that has been carried out by managers of Rumah Zakat using the RASCR framework. The results of this research will be used to make recommendations for improvements regarding which components need to be strengthened and improved so as to be able to encourage and optimize the role of the leader in improving the performance of his team through the coaching process.

B. Company Profile

The Rumah Zakat Foundation, often known as Rumah Zakat, is a philanthropic institution that manages, collects, and empowers zakat, infaq, and sadaqah funds. Other forms of generosity are implemented in a series of programs working in the fields of education, health, the economy, and the environment to create and spread happiness to people in need. These programs are integrated using a village-based community development approach called *Desa Berdaya*, with the aim of accelerating community empowerment from mustahik to muzaki.

Rumah Zakat is included in the category of *Organisasi Pengelola Zakat (OPZ)* in accordance with regulations issued by the government through the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia regarding zakat management, namely Law (UU) Number 23 of 2011 concerning Zakat Management and Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia (PP) Number 14 of 2011. 2014 Concerning Zakat Management. Based on the passion to become the best philanthropic institution in channeling happiness between donors and beneficiaries, Rumah Zakat is not only committed to being a trusted, progressive, and professional institution but can also collaborate with various parties to create empowerment for the Indonesian people. Currently, Rumah Zakat is one of the most trusted LAZNAS in the community.

C. Business Issue

Based on the results of the performance appraisal in 2022, the performance appraisal assessment conducted by Rumah Zakat is divided into four categories: excellent, good, average, and need improvement. The results of the 2022 performance appraisal indicate that 15% of employees are rated as excellent, 50% as good, 25% as average, and 10% as needing improvement. Based on this data, the combined percentage of the Average and Need Improvement categories is relatively high. Whereas, the target performance for employees at Rumah Zakat is to achieve a good score of 80%, indicating there is a gap between the condition and the target.

In this regard, the strategic step that needs to be taken is to encourage and optimize the role of leaders in improving team performance. The involvement of leaders or managers in enhancing team performance is crucial. Leaders must be able to play their role as coaches and maximize their function in the coaching process. However, in reality, there are several issues that arise from participants in the employee improvement program regarding the involvement of managers in team development, namely: lack of improvement process or guidance provided by leaders or managers to subordinates; unclear and unguided instruction about work; leaders being unable to set a good example in achieving targets or goals in work; criticizing work without providing guidance and appreciation; and lack of trust between leaders and employees. Therefore, based on the situation, there is a need for a comprehensive evaluation regarding the coaching process conducted by all managers at Rumah Zakat to immediately implement improvements and provide training so that the managers at Rumah Zakat can effectively and optimally implement coaching effectiveness

D. Research Question and Research Objective

1) Research Question

- a) How is the coaching evaluation that has been done by Leader Rumah Zakat?
- b) What are the components or competencies that are needed to strengthen and improve a leader's role in the coaching process?
- c) What recommendations can be proposed regarding coaching effectiveness programs to be able to encourage the role of the leader in optimizing team performance?

2) Research Objective

This paper aims to evaluate the current condition of implementation of the coaching process carried out by managers of Rumah Zakat and what components or competencies need to be improved by leaders in order to optimize the coaching approach in the team development process.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

II.1 The Definition of Coaching

Coaching has multiple definitions; according to Kampa-Kokesch and Anderson (2001), coaching is a form of systematic feedback intervention designed to enhance an employee's professional skills, interpersonal awareness, and personal effectiveness. Another author stated that coaching is defined as "a process of equipping people with the tools, knowledge, and opportunities they need to develop themselves and become more effective" (Peterson, 1996, p. 78). Various studies that identify a positive relationship between increased individual performance as a result of coaching practices and organizational performance use productivity to measure organizational performance (Szabo et al., 2019). Mujtaba (2007) states that coaching is "the continuous process of conversational collaborations and interactions aimed at assisting others to unlock and realize their full potential, one task and one skill at a time, and at a pace appropriate for the person being coached" (p. 3). Companies increasingly state an expectation that managers will coach their employees, with research confirming a positive correlation between coaching and employee satisfaction, individual performance, and organizational goals (Ellinger et al., 2011; Wheeler, 2011). Research also identified specific coaching behaviors as desirable in leaders, namely:

- Using listening skills and communication to involve others, setting clear performance expectations, and self-awareness (Sparks and Gentry, 2008)
- Subordinates having regular conversations with the leaders or coaches where individual and organizational goals are discussed, leaders give constructive feedback, both positive and negative, and leaders reflect on their own leadership practices (Larsson and Vinberg, 2010).

II.2 The Models of Coaching

The GROW model was developed in the late 1980s by John Whitmore and Graham Alexander (Frazier, 2016). The acronym GROW stands for Goals, Reality, Options, and Will. According to Whitmore (2017), this model aims to plan a journey. According to Stewart-Lord, Baillie, and Woods (2017), 49 leadership coaching studies using the GROW model approach revealed that success is dependent on the interaction between the managerial coach and the coaches.

The CLEAR model in the early 1980s (Bates, 2015; Frazier, 2016). The CLEAR acronym stands for Contract, Learn, Explore, Action, and Review. Beginning with the *contract*, desired outcomes, scope, and process are established. In this research, the researcher focuses on another coaching model, namely The RACSR framework was first introduced by Ting and Riddle (2006), called the five broad behavior sets (critical components). The purpose of the RACSR Framework was to provide a practical outline of various types of behavior managers could easily understand. The RASCR Framework has the more specific behavior within those sets that managers exhibit when engaging in managerial coaching. The RASCR© framework takes the five high-level critical components of managerial coaching and further divides them into nine competencies, which are each linked to behaviors (Ting & Riddle, 2006)

From a measurement perspective, specific, behavioral items that are based on frequency allow for more accurate responses (Hansbrough, Lord, & Schyns, 2015). Ultimately, the RASCR© framework is beneficial from a practical perspective, with easy-to-understand feedback for supervisors (managers) about what areas they may need to improve on to be a more effective managerial coach and exactly which behaviors they should be engaging in.

II.3 RACSR Framework

In this case, in order to enhance coaching effectiveness, it's necessary to evaluate a leader's role in the coaching process, which has been done previously through a behavioral approach using the RACSR framework. The author utilizes the RACSR framework as a tool to analyze each available critical component. There are five critical aspects provided by The Center for Creative Leadership's coaching model, namely Relationship, Assessment, Challenge, Support, and Result (RACSR), as well as nine components within each aspect. The RASCR framework is based on decades of research and experience focusing on leadership development. According to Vierra J. Anthony and Kramer Rob (2016, p. 158), it's important to have a balance of assessment, challenge, and support to facilitate development. The relationship is the most important component in the development process, where building trust between manager and employee will lead to open conversation and comfort.

II.3.1 Relationship

The *relationship* is a crucial aspect of any coaching process conducted by leaders and their subordinates. Establishing a solid relationship or partnership is critical to any coaching process (Evered & Selman, 1989; Peterson & Hicks, 1996; Levinson, 1996). In this component, there are three essential components, namely rapport, commitment, and collaboration (Ting & Riddle, 2006). There are two components in relationship aspects based on this framework:

1) *Establishing Boundaries*

Establishing boundaries has meaning establishes roles, and clarifies the purpose of the coaching relationship, there are some behavior aspects in this competency, such as clarifies supervisee expectations, discusses confidentiality and the information flow across stakeholders, clarifies roles, ground rules, session format, agenda, and manages time.

2) *Building Trust*

Building trust displays behaviors that increase the sharing of information, ideas, emotions, and insights, there are some behavior aspects in this component, such as connects almost immediately with a wide variety of supervisees, creates a safe reflective space, displays a collaborative style (verbally and non-verbally), acts from unconditional positive regard, uses humor to release tension or to address difficult topics with a light touch, displays broad knowledge and experience and matches supervisee's knowledge

II.3.2 Assessment

The Second critical component in this framework, namely *Assessment*. It focuses on assisting employees make sense of feedback as it is delivered as part of the frequent daily interactions between managers and employees, as well as in assisting employees acquire different perspectives to solve problems. The key components of an assessment as follow:

1) *Creating awareness through feedback*

Creating awareness through feedback helps others use self-reflection as a tool for clarity about their current situation. Giving and receiving feedback is critical for an effective mentoring and coaching relationship, and creating awareness through feedback is an important component of assessment in coaching (Vierra J Anthony & Kramer Rob, 2016)

2) *Encouraging self-discovery*

Encouraging self-discovery has meaning, encourages new ways of thinking where employees or coaches actively explore and understand themselves. It involved clarifying current strengths, weaknesses, values, beliefs, and potential.

II.3.3 Challenge

The aim of challenge in coaching is to build a clear picture of what is possible by questioning current constraints and helping explore new possibilities (Vierra J Anthony & Kramer Rob, 2016). In this case, the manager asks questions, encourages new ideas, and helps remove barriers/obstacles for the employee. The key components of challenge as follow:

1) *Challenges Thinking and Assumptions*

Challenging the employee without being judgmental, encouraging new ways of thinking, using generative questioning, and Pushes boundaries (supervisors and supervisees)

2) *Promotes Practice*

Encourages experimentation with new tools, models, or approaches and practices feed-forward rehearsals with the supervisee to these out in the supervision session

II.3.4 Support

Support is the third leg of the development stool, without it, a well-crafted stool will fall; with it, you have stability and the capacity to hold the weight (Ting & Riddle, 2006). Support has an important role as well in the development process, employees or coaches will feel motivated by the presence and involvement of managers in the process. The key components of support, as follows:

1) *Listening For Understanding*

According to Hunt and Weintraub (2002), failure to listen to results in a discussion where participants may become defensive, which reduces their potential to learn. By contrast, a coaching manager focuses on the coaches, in a non-judgmental and empathic way, to understand not only the facts but how the other person sees those facts and feels about them, noticing how things are said, as well as the speaker's body language and what is not said (Zeus and Skiffington, 2000).

2) *Sustaining Momentum*

In this component, managers help others stay motivated throughout the change process. According to Vierra J Anthony & Kramer Rob (2016), one of the most important roles a leader coach can play lies in helping the coaches clarify, articulate, and continuously reevaluate and reconfirm her motivations.

II.3.5 Results

Results arise from the right balance of assessment, challenge, and support in the context of an effective relationship (Ting & Riddle, 2006). The fifth component, called *result*, focuses on establishing the development plan, including activities such as setting clear goals and identifying the behaviors that will help employees achieve the goals.

1) Set Goals

The aim of competency is to help others set challenging and meaningful goals to increase their effectiveness. Employees or coaches are able to identify goals that will have the biggest impact and identify specific behavior that will lead to achieving their goals.

III. METHODOLOGY

In this chapter, the researcher will discuss the research framework for this paper, namely research design, and how to collect and analyze the data that have been gathered.

A) Research Design

Figure III.I

This figure above will explain about research design of the final project, which is part of the strategy for answering the research questions and solving a business issue. According to Sekaran (2016), research design is a plan for collecting, measuring, and analyzing data, based on research questions from studies.

B) Data Collection Method

As mentioned above in the research design, the researcher uses mixed-method research. Mixed-methods research is a research method that combines and integrates qualitative and quantitative research methods in a single research study. The questionnaires contain closed-ended questions and open-ended questions about the respondent’s identity. However, the questionnaire is made without names or anonymity to obtain honest answers. Furthermore, follow the results up with a qualitative phase by using semi-structured interviews. A semi-structured interview is a data collection method that focuses on asking questions within a preplanned topic framework. This survey will be distributed particularly to employees who have superiors (officer level) who often interact directly with their leaders at Rumah Zakat. To determine the number of samples, this paper uses Slovin’s formula with a confidence level of 95% and results of 213 with a margin of error of 5%. Siegle D (2021) stated the confidence level of 95% used by most researchers in their research; the wider the confidence interval, the more certain it could be that the whole population's answers would be within that range.

C) Data Analysis Method

After the data is collected, the researcher uses descriptive statistics analysis to ensure that the information obtained is straightforward, applicable, and comprehensible for readers. In analyzing the quantitative results, the validity and reliability of the questionnaire will be checked first. After that, describe the characteristics of the identity of respondents who have completed the questionnaire, consisting of gender, age, and working directorate. The second analysis explains the distribution of answers from respondents that have filled out the questionnaire based on each indicator of coaching effectiveness in order to be better understood and concluded from the descriptive quantitative analysis. All the data is put into three categories (low, medium, and high) in order

to be easy to analyze and understand. The last is providing the results of semi-structured interviews as validating and supporting data.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the findings of the research methodology in previous chapter. Alternative solutions will be explained based on data collection and analyzing data using appropriate methods to find the optimal solution. This chapter consists of subchapters, namely analysis, business solution, and implementation plan.

A. Analysis

This subchapter presents the results and discussion of the analysis data obtained from 213 respondents which includes respondent profiles, descriptive analysis statistic, descriptive analysis of each indicator, supporting data of qualitative analysis.

1) Respondent Profile

Based on the table below, the majority of respondents were male (51%), aged 26-30 years old (29%), working unit program (40%). There are 52 items of questionnaire that have been checked on validity and reliability which indicate valid as well as reliable.

Table IV.1 Respondent Profile

Respondent Profile	f	%
Gender		
Male	108	51%
Female	105	49%
Age		
<25 years old	21	10%
26-30 years old	62	29%
31-35 years old	49	23%
36-40 years old	44	21%
40-45 years old	27	13%
>45 years old	10	5%
Working Unit		
Marketing	66	31%
Special Directorate	13	6%
Operational	48	23%
Program	86	40%

2) The Results of Descriptive Statistics of Coaching Effectiveness

A descriptive statistical test of this variable needs to be carried out in order to see a general picture of the data, such as the average value (mean), highest value (maximum), lowest value (minimum), and standard deviation of the 9 variables from this research, namely establishing boundaries (EB), building trust (BT), creating awareness through feedback (CATF), encouraging self-discovery (ESD), challenging thinking and assumptions (CTA), promoting practice (PP), listening for understanding (LFU), sustaining momentum (SM), and setting goals (SG). The results of the descriptive statistical measurement can be seen in Table IV.1.2 as follows:

Table IV.2 The Results of Descriptive Statistic of Coaching Effectiveness

	Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std Deviation
EB	213	5	20	15.7700	3.39098
BT	213	7	28	22.4085	5.06163
CATF	213	7	28	21.4178	4.66005

ESD	213	5	20	15.3239	3.77969
CTA	213	6	24	18.0282	4.25476
PP	213	6	24	17.9531	4.28442
LFU	213	6	24	18.4977	4.05345
SM	213	6	24	19.108	4.37538
SG	213	4	16	12.5869	3.08346
Valid N (Listwise)					

Based on the results of the descriptive statistic test above, the distribution of data obtained by researcher can be concluded as follows:

- a) The table shows that the data distribution for the established boundaries (EB) variable has a minimum value of 5, a maximum value of 20, an average of 15.77, and a standard deviation of 3.39. It means that the average level of effectiveness of coaching implementation on the indicators of establishing boundaries, namely establishing roles, and clarifying the purpose of the coaching relationship is relatively large by looking at the proximity of the average value (mean) to the maximum. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is 3.39, which means that the data variance is relatively large considering the distance between the average value and standard deviation.
- b) The table shows that the data distribution for the build trust (BT) variable has a minimum value of 7, a maximum value of 28, an average (mean) of 22.40, and a standard deviation of 5.06. It means that the average level of effectiveness of coaching implementation on the builds trust (BT) indicator displays behaviors that increase the sharing of information, ideas, emotions, and insights is relatively large considering the proximity of the average value (mean) to the maximum value. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is 5.06, which means that the data variance is relatively large considering the distance between the average value (mean) and standard deviation.
- c) The table shows that the data distribution for the variable creates awareness through feedback (CATF) has a minimum value of 7, a maximum value of 28, an average (mean) of 21.41, and a standard deviation of 4.66. It means that the average level of effectiveness of coaching implementation on the indicator creating awareness through feedback (CATF) by displaying behavior that helps employees use self-reflection as a tool for clarity about their current situation is relatively large by looking at the proximity of the average value (mean) to the maximum value. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is 4.66, which means that the data variance is relatively large considering the distance between the average value (mean) and standard deviation.
- d) The table shows that the data distribution for the encouraging self-discovery (ESD) variable has a minimum value of 5, a maximum value of 20, an average (mean) of 15.32, and a standard deviation of 3.77. It means that the average level of effectiveness of coaching implementation on the indicator encouraging self-discovery (ESD) by displaying behavior encouraging new ways of thinking where employees or coaches actively explore and understand themselves is relatively large by looking at the proximity of the average value (mean) to the maximum value. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is 3.77, which means that the data variance is relatively large considering the distance between the average value (mean) and standard deviation.
- e) The table shows that the data distribution for the challenging thinking and assumptions (CTA) variable has a minimum value of 6, a maximum value of 24, an average (mean) of 18.02, and a standard deviation of 4.25. It means that the average level of effectiveness of coaching implementation on the challenging thinking and assumptions (CTA) indicator by displaying behavior that encourages new ways of thinking and challenges the supervisee without being judgmental is relatively large by looking at the proximity of the average value (mean) to the maximum value. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is 4.25, which means that the data variance is relatively large considering the distance between the average value (mean) and the standard deviation.
- f) The table shows that the data distribution for the variable promoting practice (PP) has a minimum value of 6, a maximum value of 24, an average (mean) of 17.95, and a standard deviation of 4.28. It means that the average level of effectiveness of coaching implementation on the indicator of promoting practice (PP) by displaying behavior that encourages experimentation with new tools, models, or approaches is relatively large considering the proximity of the average value

(mean) to the maximum value. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is 4.28, which means that the data variance is relatively large considering the distance between the average value (mean) and standard deviation.

- g) The table shows that the data distribution for the listening for understanding (LFU) variable has a minimum value of 6, a maximum value of 24, an average (mean) of 18.49, and a standard deviation of 4.05. It means that the average level of effectiveness of coaching implementation on the listening for understanding (LFU) indicator by displaying behavior to truly hear what others are trying to say is relatively large by looking at the proximity of the average value (mean) to the maximum value. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is 4.05, which means that the data variance is relatively large considering the distance between the average value (mean) and the standard deviation.
 - h) The table shows that the data distribution for the sustaining momentum (SM) variable has a minimum value of 6, a maximum value of 24, an average (mean) of 19.10, and a standard deviation of 4.37. It means that the average level of effectiveness of coaching implementation on the sustaining momentum (SM) indicator by displaying behavior to help others stay motivated throughout the change process is relatively large considering the proximity of the average value (mean) to the maximum value. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is 4.37, which means that the data variance is relatively large considering the distance between the average value (mean) and standard deviation.
 - i) The table shows that the data distribution for the setting goals (SG) variable has a minimum value of 4, a maximum value of 16, an average (mean) of 12.58, and a standard deviation of 3.08. It means that the average level of effectiveness of coaching implementation on the set goals (SG) indicator by displaying behavior that focuses on implementing the development plan, including activities such as setting clear goals and identifying the behaviors that will help employees achieve the goals is relatively large considering the proximity of the average value (mean) to the maximum value. Meanwhile, the standard deviation is 3.08, which means that the data variance is relatively large considering the distance between the average value (mean) and standard deviation.
- 3) Descriptive Analysis of Each Indicator of Coaching Effectiveness

The description of the analysis of each indicator from the evaluation of coaching effectiveness implementation is the result of statements regarding 5 components, which have 9 indicators that are measured using a Likert scale from 1-4. Sugiyono (2010: 93) said that the Likert scale is used to measure the attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. Afterwards, all the data is put into three categories (low, medium, and high) in order to be easy to analyze and understand.

Table IV.3 The Result of Each Indicator of Coaching Effectiveness

Area	Indicator	Level	Freq	%
Relation	Establishes Boundaries	Low	30	14.1%
		Medium	130	61.0%
		High	53	24.9%
	Builds Trust	Low	32	15.0%
		Medium	117	55.0%
		High	64	30.0%
Assessment	Creates Awareness Though Feedback	Low	33	15.5%
		Medium	135	63.4%
		High	45	21.1%
	Encouraging self-discovery	Low	41	19.2%
		Medium	117	54.9%
		High	55	25.8%
Challenge	Challenges Thinking and Assumptions	Low	36	16.9%
		Medium	126	59.2%

	Promotes Practice	High	51	23.9%
		Low	39	18.3%
		Medium	124	58.2%
		High	50	23.5%
Support	Listening For Understanding	Low	26	12.2%
		Medium	151	70.9%
		High	36	16.9%
	Sustaining Momentum	Low	33	15.5%
		Medium	112	52.6%
		High	68	31.9%
Results	Set Goals	Low	40	18.8%
		Medium	112	52.6%
		High	61	28.6%

Based on the results of each indicator of coaching effectiveness, we concluded that, as follow:

- a) The established Boundaries indicator have a medium level with a frequency of 130, or 61%, while the low level has a frequency of 30 or 14% and the high level has a frequency of 53, or 25%. It concluded that the established boundaries tend to medium level, which means that respondents indicated that the involvement of managers in implementing the coaching process, particularly in establishing roles and clarifying the purpose of the coaching relationship, is considered quite optimal and has been implemented; however, the number of frequencies in the high category which is 53 or 25% indicates that it has not reached an effective level.
- b) The builds trust indicator has a medium level with a frequency of 117 or 55%, while the low level has a frequency of 32 or 15% and the high level has a frequency of 64 or 30%. In the previous research show that an important contributor to employee success is the employee's relationship with the manager. A supportive working relationship can build enthusiasm and commitment to continuous performance improvement (Moss & Sanchez, 2004). It concluded that the building trust tend to medium level, which means that respondents indicated that the involvement of managers in implementing the coaching process, by displaying behavior that increase the sharing of information, ideas, emotion and insights, are considered quite optimal and has been implemented; however, the number of frequencies in the high category which is 64 or 30% indicates that it has not reached an effective level.
- c) Creating awareness through feedback in the table above have a medium level of 135 frequency or 63%, while the low level has a 33 frequency or 16% and the high level has a 45 frequency or 30%. Based on a literature review, giving and receiving feedback is critical to an effective mentoring and coaching relationship, and creating awareness through feedback is an important component of assessment in coaching (Vierra J Anthony & Kramer Rob, 2016). It concluded that creating awareness through feedback tend to medium level, which means that respondents indicated that the involvement of managers in implementing the coaching process, by helping employee use self-reflection as a tool for clarity about their current situations and give feedback constructively are considered quite optimal and has been implemented; however, the number of frequencies in the high category which is 45 or 21% indicates that it has not reached an effective level.
- d) Encouraging self-discovery based on the table above have a medium level with a frequency of 117 or 55%, while the low level has 41 frequency or 19% and the level high has 55 frequency or 26%. It concluded that encouraging self-discovery tend to medium level, which means that respondents indicated that the involvement of managers in implementing the coaching process, by encouraging new ways of thinking where employees or coaches actively explore and understand themselves are considered quite optimal and has been implemented; however, the number of frequencies in the high category which is 55 or 25% indicates that it has not reached an effective level.

- e) Challenges thinking and assumptions based on the table above have a medium level with a frequency of 126 or 59%, while the low level has a 36 frequency or 17% and the high level has a frequency of 51 or 26%. It concluded that challenges thinking and assumptions tend to medium level, which means that respondents indicated that the involvement of managers in implementing the coaching process, by challenging the employee without being judgmental, encouraging new ways of thinking and using generative questioning are considered quite optimal and has been implemented; however, the number of frequencies in the high category which is 51 or 23% indicates that it has not reached an effective level.
- f) Meanwhile, the promotes practice indicator based on the table have a medium level with a frequency of 124 or 58%, while the low level has a 39 frequency or 18% and the high level has a 50 frequency or 24%. It concluded that promoted practice tend to medium level, which means that respondents indicated that the involvement of managers in implementing the coaching process, by encouraging experimentation with new tools, models or approaches are considered quite optimal and has been implemented; however, the number of frequencies in the high category which is 50 or 23% indicates that it has not reached an effective level.
- g) Listening for understanding in the table above have a medium level with a frequency of 151 or 71%, while the low level has a 26 frequency or 12% and the high level has a 36 frequency or 17%. According to Hunt and Weintraub (2002), failure to listen to results in a discussion where participants may become defensive, which reduces their potential to learn. It concluded that listening for understanding tend to medium level, which means that respondents indicated that the involvement of managers in implementing the coaching process, by using active listening skill to truly hear what others are trying to say, show curiosity, and works with emotions are considered quite optimal and has been implemented; however, the number of frequencies in the high category which is 36 or 16% indicates that it has not reached an effective level.
- h) Meanwhile, the sustaining momentum from the table above have medium level with a frequency of 112 or 53%, while the low level has a 33 frequency or 15% and the high level has 36 frequency or 12%. It concluded that sustaining momentum tend to medium level, which means that respondents indicated that the involvement of managers in implementing the coaching process, by helping others stay motivated throughout the change process, providing recognition and encouragement, recognizing strengths are considered quite optimal and has been implemented; however, the number of frequencies in the high category which is 68 or 31% indicates that it has not reached an effective level.
- i) The set goals in the table above have a medium level of 112 frequency or 52%, while the low level has 40 frequency or 19% and the high level has a 61 frequency or 29%. It concluded that set goals tend to medium level, which means that respondents indicated that the involvement of managers in implementing the coaching process, by helping others set challenging and meaningful goals to increase their effectiveness, identifying goals that will have the biggest impact and specific behavior that will lead to achieving their goals are considered quite optimal and has been implemented; however, the number of frequencies in the high category which is 61 or 28% indicates that it has not reached an effective level.

4) Supporting Data of Qualitative Analysis

The results of semi-structured interviews that have been conducted with key persons at Rumah Zakat show that the coaching process that has been carried out has not reached the optimal level, according to the results of surveys that have been conducted previously. Even though it has been implemented, there are several aspects that need to be improved. Especially in the relationship between managers and employees. Building closeness and trust in this matter is very important because, after all, it will affect the next process. Lack of appreciation from leaders for employees and lack of encouragement in employee development are things that need to be fixed.

In addition, the perceived obstacle to creating a feedback culture involves difficulties in conveying feedback with an approach that does not offend employees. Another challenge is ensuring each employee or team receives feedback on their work progress, which requires improved communication skills from managers. There are other things that need to be considered and emphasized regarding the definition of coaching itself. It is important to equalize the perception that the coaching process does not have to be formal. Concerns arise if a leader feels they have been coached but employees feel otherwise. Equating perceptions of behavior and the ongoing coaching process need to be conveyed to both of them.

To maintain the sustainability of coaching implementation, it is recommended to optimize the momentum of performance appraisals carried out every quarter. This needs to be supported by policies that provide specific time for the coaching process, with integration

into the system to facilitate monitoring and documentation. In addition, the commitment of the leader to be actively involved in the development process also plays an important role in this context. In order to improve the effectiveness of coaching in the future, continuous training related to coaching and strengthening the perception of coaching among employees are needed. It is also recommended that there are special guidelines that require each employee to receive coaching at least 2-3 times a year, which can be integrated into the key objectives of each leader. More optimally, if a template is made that is added with a notification feature as a reminder of the series of coaching processes that have been carried out by leaders, In addition to providing convenience, this can function as a monitoring and controlling part for the development and training (LND) department.

B. Business Solution

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted, it indicates that the implementation of coaching effectiveness tends to be at a medium level, which means that the coaching process has been implemented and is quite optimal, but the assessment is still in the medium stage, so improvements need to be made. The following proposed solutions can be implemented in order to increase effectiveness and have a significant impact:

a) Training Program

Enhancing coaching skills is an important component of leadership development (Ellinger et al., 2003). Debriefing and re-strengthening related to coaching skills need to be done for all Rumah Zakat managers, particularly understanding how the coaching process works and what behaviors need to be shown and considered in order to help improve the effectiveness of coaching implementation among managers and employees. Here are some aspects that can be focused on in debriefing:

- Relationship Skill

Strengthening aspects of relationship skills can help managers optimize the relationship between leaders and subordinates. A good relationship can be developed by asking specific questions about subordinates' interests outside of work, background, and view of the world. In the relationship component, finding commonalities is another effective way to establish rapport (Ting & Riddle, 2006). Forming a good relationship can start with a non-formal approach because it can help develop a relationship between both of them.

- Interpersonal Skill

Good interpersonal skills could have a positive impact on the change process of employees, particularly by showing positive intentions through behaviors in the coaching process. Skills that can be strengthened include great and effective communication skills, active listening, how to show empathy, building teamwork, and skills in managing conflict.

b) Continuous Assessment and Feedback

Managers could continuously assess employee progress with an intensity of at least once a month. Providing regular feedback can identify any areas of development that need immediate attention. This can be supported by mandatory policies or rules informed by the company to superordinate by being integrated through the system with the aim of making it easier and more documented. Research also identified specific coaching behaviors as desirable in leaders, namely, subordinates having regular conversations with the leaders or coaches where individual and organizational goals are discussed, leaders giving constructive feedback, both positive and negative, and leaders reflecting on their own leadership practices (Larsson and Vinberg, 2010).

c) Outbound Program

Company could facilitate outbound programs that involve leaders and employees in order to increase engagement and relationships between of them. This outbound could be used as a form of learning in order to explore new ideas and train leaders and subordinates to produce alternative and impactful solutions.

d) Regular and Scheduled Meetings

Regular and scheduled meetings between managers and employees need to be conducted as part of the leader's commitment to helping individuals succeed in achieving the desired goals. On the other hand, the regular meeting could be used as a place for celebration, appreciation, and support for all processes that have been carried out by employees. The performance appraisal process that is carried out quarterly can be optimized with the company giving a special time so that the assessment and review process can be carried out optimally.

e) Individual Development Plan

Individual development plans need to be applied by managers to their subordinates as part of tools to help in recognizing the strengths, weaknesses, and development needs of each employee. Through this tool, managers could find out which areas need to

be developed in order to support the achievement of the desired goals. Individual development plan could be supported or facilitated by Human Capital Management so that the template or format used is the same.

C. Implementation Plan

The findings of this study indicate that the effectiveness of coaching in various components of Rumah Zakat is still in the medium stage, which means that improvements need to be made. Several proposed solutions have been submitted to relevant stakeholders or divisions that are closely related to the people development process, namely the Learning & Development Department as the person in charge. The first proposed solution related to the training program has been agreed upon and will be included in the development plan for managers, which will be implemented in early 2024, precisely in February.

Afterwards, continuous assessment and feedback at Rumah Zakat already exists, but so far it is still done manually and is not optimal; therefore, in order to facilitate monitoring and be well documented, it is necessary to integrate into the system, and this will be discussed with the technology and management department at Rumah Zakat. Regular and scheduled meetings, particularly during the performance appraisal process, which is carried out quarterly, could provide time that requires each leader to meet regularly by discussing, assessing, and reviewing optimally related employee performance. In early 2024, the individual development plan itself will begin to be optimized, and in this case, the Learning & Development Department, as the person in charge, will ensure that this individual development plan can run as expected.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter consists of elaborations as well as details of conclusions drawn from analysis and interpretation results based on the findings in the previous chapter. A summary of recommendations for related stakeholders as listed in the proposed implementation plan will also be provided in this chapter, as well as future research suggestions

A) Conclusion

Based on the research that has been conducted by the author, several points related to this research can be concluded, there are:

- a) The current condition is related to the effectiveness of the implementation of the coaching process carried out by Rumah Zakat managers using the RACSR model approach, which consists of five important aspects, including relationship, assessment, challenge, support, and results, as well as nine components, namely establishing boundaries (EB), building trust (BT), creating awareness through feedback (CATF), encouraging self-discovery (ESD), challenging thinking and assumptions (CTA), promoting practice (PP), listening for understanding (LFU), sustaining momentum (SM), and setting goals (SG), which are at the medium level, which means that they have been implemented however still need to be improved.
- b) From the analysis of the previous chapter, the components that need to be strengthened and improved certainly refer to all aspects and components in it. Based on the RACSR model, coaching effectiveness will be achieved if all aspects of it can be implemented properly and the relationship is the most important component in the development process, where building trust between manager and employee will lead to open conversation and comfort.

B) Recommendation

This recommendation is presented with the expectation that it can yield benefits and positive contributions to the academic field, serving as a valuable source of information and consideration for practitioners. For stakeholders, especially the relevant department overseeing learning and development, the author suggests conducting a comprehensive evaluation of the coaching process every semester. This will enable the identification of areas for improvement on a regular basis, ensuring the optimal implementation of the coaching process. Immediate action can then be taken to address any issues that require improvement.

Next, the author suggests that learning and development can identify and make specific policies related to the coaching process to be implemented. Understanding related to coaching also needs to be strengthened between managers and employees so that there are no differences of opinion regarding the definition of coaching itself and the objectives of this coaching can be achieved. Regarding this study finding, researchers in the future may be able to analyze more deeply each component in the RACSR model with the same analysis approach using data categorization in order to produce a more comprehensive description. Researchers also hope that in the future there will be many studies related to evaluating the effectiveness of coaching using this model in other institutions or companies by involving more other perspectives in the evaluation process.

REFERENCES

1. Bates, R. (2004). A critical analysis of evaluation practice: the Kirkpatrick model and the principle of beneficence. *Ethics, Evaluation and For-Profit Corporations*, 27(3), 341– 347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.evalprogplan.2004.04.011>
2. Ellinger, A. D., Ellinger, A. E., & Keller, S. B. (2003). *Supervisory coaching behavior, employee satisfaction, and warehouse employee performance: A dyadic perspective in the distribution industry*. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, 14, 435–458.
3. Ellinger, A.D., Ellinger, A.E., Bachrach, D.G., Wang, Y.-L. and Bas, A.B.E. (2011), “Organizational investments in social capital, managerial coaching, and employee work-related performance”, *Management Learning*, Vol. 42 No. 1, pp. 67-85.
4. Evered, R. D., & Selman, J. C. (1989). *Coaching and the art of management*. *Organizational Dynamics*, 18, 16–32. doi:10.1016/0090-2616(89)90040-5
5. Frazier, K. L. (2016). *Planning, implementing, and evaluating manager-as-coach programs in business: a Delphi study*. [Doctoral dissertation, Pepperdine University]. Pepperdine Digital Commons. <https://digitalcommons.pepperdine.edu/etd/743>
6. Hall, D. T., Otazo, K. L., & Hollenbeck, G. P. (1999). *Behind closed doors: What really happens in executive coaching*. *Organizational Dynamics*, 27, 39–53.
7. Hansbrough, T. K., Lord, R. G., & Schyns, B. (2015). *Reconsidering the accuracy of follower leadership ratings*. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 26, 220-237. doi:10.1016/j.leaqua.2014.11.006
8. Hunt, J. M., & Weintraub J. R. (2004). *Learning developmental coaching*. *Journal of Management Education*, 28(1), 39–61.
9. Hunt, J. M., & Weintraub, J. R. (2002). *The coaching manager: Developing top talent in business*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
10. Kampa-Kokesch, S., & Anderson, M. Z. (2001). *Executive coaching: A comprehensive review of the literature*. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 53(4), 205–228.
11. Larsson, J. and Vinberg, S. (2010), “Leadership behaviour in successful organisations: universal or situation-dependent?”, *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, Vol. 21 No. 3, pp. 317-334.
12. Levinson, D. (1996) *Seasons of a Woman's Life*. Alfred A. Knopf, New York.
13. Mace, M.L. & Mahler, W.R. (1958). *On-the-job coaching*. In H. F. Merrill & E. Marting (Eds.). *Developing Executive Skills*. New York, NY: AMA.
14. Mujtaba, B. (2007). *Coaching and performance management: Developing and inspiring*. Davie, FL: ILEAD Academy, LLC
15. Peterson, D. and Hicks, M.D. (1996) *Leader as Coach: Strategies for Coaching and Developing Others*. Personnel Decisions International Corporation, Minneapolis.
16. Peterson, D. B. (1996). *Executive coaching at work: The art of one-on-one change*. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 48, 78–86. doi:10.1037//1061-4087.48.2.78
17. Peterson, D. B. 1996. *Executive coaching at work: The art of one-on-one change*. *Consulting Psychology Journal: Practice and Research*, 48, 78–86.
18. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods for Business. A skill Building Approach*. 7th ed. Chichester: Wiley.
19. Siegle D (2021), *Confidence Intervals and Levels*, Neag School of Education – University of Connecticut. Retrieved <https://researchbasics.education.uconn.edu/confidence-intervals-and-levels/>
20. Stewart-Lord, A., Baillie, L., & Woods, S. (2017). *Health care staff perceptions of a coaching and mentoring programme: A qualitative case study evaluation*. *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, Vol 15, Iss 2, Pp 70-85 (2017), 70. <https://doi.org/10.24384/000251>.
21. Sugiyono. 2010. *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta
22. Szabó, S., Slavić, A., & Berber, N. (2019). *Coaching and its effects on individual and organizational performances in Central and Eastern Europe*. *Anali Ekonomskog Fakulteta u Subotici*, 55(41), 67–80. <https://doi.org/10.5937/anebsub1941067s>

23. Ting, S., & Riddle, D. (2006). *A framework for leadership development coaching*. In S. Ting & P. Scisco (Eds.) *The CCL Handbook of coaching* (pp. 34-62). San Francisco: JosseyBass/Wiley.
24. Vierra J Anthony & Kramer Rob. (2016), *Management and Leadership Skills for Medical Faculty*, Springer. New York Heidelberg Dordrecht London, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-27781-3
25. Wheeler, L. (2011), "How does the adoption of coaching behaviours by line managers contribute to the achievement of organisational goals?", *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 1-15, available at: www.business.brookes.ac.uk/research/areas/coachingandmentoring/view.asp?issue¼vol09issue1
26. Whitmore, J. (2017). *Coaching for Performance, The principles and practices of coaching and leadership*. 5th Ed. London: Nicholas Brealey Publishing
27. Zeus, P. and Skiffington, S. (2000), *Complete Guide to Coaching at Work*, McGraw-Hill, Sydney

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